

Metabolic responses of naphthalene acetic acid application and *Rhizobium* inoculation on green gram (*Vigna radiata*)

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Abstract : Effect of *Rhizobium* inoculation and foliar application and pre-soaking of seeds with naphthalene acetic acid alone and in different combinations, was studied on the metabolisms of various biomolecules. Both, naphthalene acetic acid and *Rhizobium* treatments showed increased pigment profiles, photosynthetic activity and improved biosynthesis of carbohydrate and total protein. Total nitrogen content in leaves as well as seed was significantly increased in all the treatment combinations. Significant change in amino acid composition was also observed.

Keywords : Metabolic response, *Vigna radiata*, *Rhizobium* inoculation, naphthalene acetic acid.

Introduction

India is the major pulses growing country and occupies one third of the total world's cropped area and one fourth of the total production. In India, pulses cover about 3.34 million ha with an annual production of 1.06 million tons¹. Pulses play an important role in agricultural economy of the country. Green gram (*Vigna radiata*), commonly known as 'mung bean', is one of the most important and short duration pulse crop grown in India. Green gram is highly nutritious containing 23–24% protein and small amount of carbohydrates, minerals and vitamins. Germinating seed synthesizes remarkable quantity of ascorbic acid. Green gram also contains appreciable amount of riboflavin and thiamine². Cultivation of *Vigna radiata* (L) during rainy season is constrained largely due to weather observation and its vulnerability to diseases and pest resulting in poor and unstable productivity³. In general, the productivity of pulses could be increased by inoculating the seeds with appropriate strain of *Rhizobium*. *Rhizobium* has the capacity to fix the atmospheric nitrogen in symbiotic association with legume and certain non legume⁴. Plant growth regulators are chemical messenger regulating various physiological and metabolic responses. Many workers observed the effect of various plant regulators on germination, growth, flowering, and fruit set. On very low concentration, the growth regulators modulate RNA and protein synthesis⁵. Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) being a synthetic auxin, is dependent on

membrane receptors in the plant cell which is a pre requisite for auxin action. Auxin may be inter related with a repressor compound in an auxin regulated gene and inactivate it. The rate of photosynthesis upon the carbon diffusion process and this in turn depends upon stomata conductance. In legumes, the photosynthetic rate during vegetative stage has more pronounced effect on the total dry matter production. It is also reported that the photosynthetic rate declined sharply as pod began to develop, which was further associated with fall in total nitrogen, protein and carbohydrate^{6,7}. Considering the above facts, the present investigation was conducted with the aim to study the biochemical changes induced with the application of NAA and *Rhizobium* inoculation in green gram with special reference to vegetative and reproductive parts.

Results and discussion

Observations on chlorophyll and carotenoids contents and their correlation coefficient are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The chlorophyll content was significantly less in leaves and green seeds of plants treated with NAA alone as compared to combined application of NAA and *Rhizobium*. However, chlorophyll content in green seeds was at par in 100 ppm NAA and *Rhizobium* alone to the combined treatment of both. Irrespective of DAS, the highest chlorophyll content in leaves and green seeds was observed in *Rhizobium* + 50 ppm NAA treated plants. Both,

Table 1. Chlorophyll and carotenoids contents in leaves and green seeds

Treatment combinations	Chlorophyll content (ppm)						Carotenoids content (ppm)					
	Leaves			Green seeds			Leaves			Green seeds		
	DAS			DAS			DAS			DAS		
	30	45	60	30	45	60	30	45	60	30	45	60
50 ppm NAA	135	120	150	128	150	230	120	186	250	130	145	250
100 ppm NAA	150	174	150	150	150	340	145	146	250	138	160	300
<i>Rhizobium</i>	130	180	320	180	175	395	100	125	300	150	155	430
<i>Rhizobium</i> + 50 ppm NAA	250	250	300	180	235	458	150	155	320	400	425	440
<i>Rhizobium</i> + 100 ppm NAA	270	260	230	95	175	380	130	140	280	375	270	335
Control	135	135	148	120	120	148	75	75	80	120	130	125
CD ($P = 5$)	070 ^{NS}			120			80			100 ^{NS}		

CD - Critical difference.

Table 2. Correlation analysis of chlorophyll and carotenoid contents in mung bean

DAS	Chlorophyll content (ppm)								DAS	Carotenoids content (ppm)							
	DAS									DAS							
	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65		30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65
30									30								
35	96								35	61							
40	98	93							40	61	63						
45	98	96	83						45	67	67	68					
50	93	96	87	83					50	63	67	68	62				
55	92	93	83	87	78				55	64	68	71	61	54			
60	96	98	87	84	75	77			60	67	61	61	61	58	58		
65	98	94	91	86	81	73	71		65	68	6	57	59	56	56	55	

in leaves and green seeds, the chlorophyll content increased with increasing age of plants. At later stage of plant growth (60 DAS), the chlorophyll content was higher in green seeds as compared to leaves. Similarly, the carotenoid content was higher in green seeds as compared to leaves. Carotenoid content ranged from 100 ppm to 320 ppm in leaves and 128 ppm to 425 ppm in green seeds. The carotenoid content was significantly less in leaves as well as green seeds of plants treated with *Rhizobium* and NAA alone as compared to combined treatment of both. However, carotenoid content in leaves and green seeds was negatively related to the concentration of NAA used and decreased with increasing concentration of NAA. The carotenoid content increased with increasing age of plants in both, leaves and green seeds, and was highest (440 ppm) in green seeds treated with *Rhizobium* + 50 ppm NAA after 60 days of sowing. Significant increase in chlorophyll content after supplementation of *Rhizobium* have earlier been reported in mung bean⁸. NAA application might be responsible for wider opening of stomata⁹.

A significant increase in carbohydrate content in leaves was observed in all the treatment except 100 ppm NAA which was at par to the control. It is found that chlorophyll and carotenoids contents to be decreasing trend up to 40 DAS and declined significantly at 45 DAS. Maximum chlorophyll content was reported at 30 DAS whereas maximum carotenoids were observed at 40 DAS (Table 2). Total chlorophyll and carotenoids contents showed positive and significant correlation with plant and seed age, maximum the age minimum the chlorophyll and carotenoids. Grain legumes accumulate large quantities of nitrogen balance in plant and seeds. It has been suggested that leaf nitrogen is remobilized for seed development and cause a decline in photosynthesis. Increasing age of plants has no bearing on carbohydrate content as evident from Table 3. The maximum carbohydrate content was observed in leaves of *Rhizobium* + 50 ppm NAA treated plants followed by *Rhizobium* treatment alone and *Rhizobium* + 100 ppm NAA. The maximum carbohydrate content (2560 ppm) was observed in green seeds at later

Table 3. Protein and carbohydrate content in leaves and green seeds of mung bean

Treatment combinations	Protein content (ppm)						Carbohydrate content (ppm)					
	Leaves			Green seeds			Leaves			Green seeds		
	DAS			DAS			DAS			DAS		
	30	45	60	30	45	60	30	45	60	30	45	60
50 ppm NAA	1500	1500	1550	1820	1800	1820	2010	2050	2010	2730	2750	2750
100 ppm NAA	1170	1150	1150	1500	1520	1520	2170	2150	2170	2530	2530	2550
<i>Rhizobium</i>	1880	1870	2100	2100	2500	2560	2300	2380	2340	2890	2880	2880
<i>Rhizobium</i> + 50 ppm NAA	2040	2040	2020	2300	2360	2360	2450	2400	2450	2650	2640	2650
<i>Rhizobium</i> + 100 ppm NAA	1750	1750	1760	2170	2170	2150	2870	2820	2860	2510	2520	2520
Control	1130	1170	1150	1190	1180	1200	2140	2180	2160	2310	2310	2350
CD ($P = 5$)	5			20			100			180 ^{NS}		

stage (60 DAS) in *Rhizobium* alone treated plants followed by *Rhizobium* + 50 ppm NAA. Hormonal treatment and salinity were found to significantly increase the carbohydrate content in many plants¹⁰.

Amino acids, glycine, valine, arginine, leucine, alanine, lysine, histidine, serine, proline, asparagine, threonine and tyrosine were characterized in chromatograms during different stages of seed development (Table 4). Favorable effects of NAA and *Rhizobium* application was observed metabolisms of the plant. However, the sulphur containing amino acid is conspicuously absent throughout the present investigation. All the amino acids analyzed were found more or less abundantly at later stages of seed development except proline which was not observed at any stage of seed development. Lysine was found abundantly at all stages of seed development whereas,

Table 4. *Rhizobium* and NAA induced changes in amino acid composition of green gram seeds

Amino acids	DAS								
	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	65
Glycine	-	-	-	±	+	+	++	++	++
Valine	+	±	±	±	±	++	++	++	++
Arginine	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	++	++
Leucine	-	±	±	±	+	+	+	+	+
Alanine	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	++	++
Lysine	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++
Histidine	-	-	-	±	+	+	+	+	+
Serine	±	±	±	+	+	+	++	++	++
Proline	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Asparagine	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Threonine	-	-	±	±	+	++	++	++	++
Tyrosine	++	++	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

(+) Present, (±) almost absent, (++) abundant, (-) absent.

valine, leucine, serine and threonine were absent or almost absent during the initial stages seed development. Tyrosine was found abundantly at initial stages seed development and development. Tyrosine was found abundantly at initial stages seed development and decreased with increasing age of seeds. Significant increase in total protein was observed in all the treatments against control. This may be due to activation of protein synthesis exerted by the exogenous phytohormones treatments¹¹. The maximum protein content was recorded in seeds of *Rhizobium* treated plants followed by *Rhizobium* + 50 ppm NAA. No significant change in protein content was observed with the increasing age of plants in any treatment combination including control. Increased nitrogen level in leaf led to increase seed protein¹². *Rhizobium* inoculation significantly affected seed protein and carbohydrates. It seems that the higher nodule dry weight, root and shoot N contents supplied sufficient N for synthesis of amino acids (the building block of protein) that translated in seed proteins^{13,14}.

The present findings are in conformity¹⁴, with regard carbohydrate, total protein, chlorophyll, carotenoids, and dry matter production recorded positively significant. These treatment combinations were found superior over the control, and found to be more effective and produced better yield through positive effects on yield components when compared to control. Hence *Rhizobium* and NAA alone and in combination could be better utilized for qualitative traits.

Experimental

The experiment was conducted at agricultural research field of Allahabad Agricultural Institute-Deemed Univer-

sity, Allahabad. The experiment was laid out in 3 m × 5 m fractional randomized block design. Two levels of NAA were used separately as well as in combination with *Rhizobium* inoculation along with check. The experiment was replicated thrice. NAA were used for pre-soaking of seed as well as for foliar application. The *Rhizobium* inoculation was done at the time of field preparations. 5 g sample (leaves and green seeds) were collected separately after 30 DAS, 45 DAS and 60 DAS for the estimation of chlorophyll, carotenoids, carbohydrates and protein. Collected leaf samples were thoroughly washed with distilled water and further used for biochemical analysis.

Chlorophyll estimation :

For total chlorophyll estimation, 1.0 g fresh leaf sample and green seeds from each treatment combination were grounded separately in 80% acetone. Extracted pulp was centrifuged and supernatant was removed. The absorbance of extract was recorded at 663, 645 nm wavelength using spectrophotometer (Systronic) against the blank⁶. The total chlorophyll content quantified¹⁵.

Carotenoids estimation :

The total carotenoids was extracted from each sample and partitioned in organic solvent acetone and hexane (2 : 3). The separation of individual component was effected by column chromatography on activated diatomaceous earth. Absorbance was recorded using spectrophotometer at 430 nm wavelength¹⁶.

Estimation of total carbohydrate :

Presence of carbohydrate in leaf and seed sample was confirmed through Benedict's and Barfoed test. Total carbohydrate was determined separately in leaves as well as green seed samples through phenol sulphuric acid methods. 1.0 g leaf and seed samples were homogenized separately in 80% hot ethanol for removal of sugars¹⁵. The sample were centrifuged and the residue was collected and resuspended in 52% perchloric acid. The samples were again centrifuged and supernatant was collected in fresh tube. Further, 5% phenol and 96% sulphuric acid were added to it. The absorption was taken at 490 nm wavelength using spectrophotometer¹⁶.

Characterization of amino acid and estimation of total protein :

Amino acids were analyzed at various stages of seed development through Paper chromatography^{15,17}. The total

protein in each sample was estimated using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent¹⁵. Absorbance was recorded at 660 nm wavelength using spectrophotometer. The total protein content was also determined by nitrogen estimation. Micro-kjeldhal technique was employed for the estimation of nitrogen content.

Following the standard procedure the data obtained in respect of various observations were statistically analyzed¹⁸. The significance of "P" value was tested at 5% level of significance. The critical difference value was determined.

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